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ENGINEERING EDUCATION RESEARCH IN THE NORDIC COUNTRIES: SCIENTOMETRIC INSIGHTS INTO PUBLICATION AND CAREER PATTERNS.

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ABSTRACT

This study analyses 3237 publications from 76 Nordic authors and provides data on the percentage of these that are educationally focused and how this in turn impacts the authors' h-index. We also calculated how early in their career they published their first educational paper.

The results provide insights into the comparative evolution of engineering education research (EER) in these countries and identify both points in common and differences in the research publication trends in the four countries. Authors from Denmark, Sweden and Finland published more educational publications than non-educational throughout their careers. Apart from Denmark, the h-index of these Nordic researchers tended to be driven by non-EER publications. Researchers in our sample, apart from those in Norway, began publishing in engineering education (EE) early in their publishing careers.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Over the last decade there has been a growing interest in the evolution of engineering education research (EER) and a variety of approaches have been adopted to study this process. Froyd and Lohman [1] used criteria for defining the field of science education research [2] to point out that while engineering education has been seen as an area of interest for educators since the end of the 19th century, over the last two decades there have been significant indicators of a transition to an interdisciplinary, more scholarly field of scientific inquiry into engineering education. Borrego and Bernhard [3] have compared Northern and Central European approaches to EER with those of the U.S. using a framework from the European *didaktik* tradition, which focuses on answering the w-questions of education. Borrego and Olds [4] employed an analysis of National Science Foundation funded projects

as a way of characterizing development in EER in the US while Williams and Alias [5] used a scientometric approach to track the evolution of EER in Malaysia.

Neto and Williams [6] analysed historical studies of the European Journal of Engineering Education (EJEE) to provide insights on the European context. Other studies looked at specific European national contexts [7, 8, 9, 10].

Strobel and colleagues at Purdue University applied bibliometric analysis to gauge the presence of interdisciplinarity in EER [11] and the growth of loose networks within the EER community [12].

1.2 Motivation

The above studies used human-curated approaches, and this limited them to analysing relatively small data sets. More recently with increased access to computer-processing power there has been growing interest in employing machine-curated analysis as this permits scientometric analysis of large volumes of data [13,14, 15, 16].

A 2018 study by Edstrom et al. [8] presented a global analysis of 160 publications from the four Nordic countries between 2000 and 2014. Their findings suggested that Nordic authors had been publishing steadily over the four years without signs of a clear evolution during the period.

The present study takes a more in-depth look at EER evolution in the four Nordic countries by employing a computer-facilitated analysis to identify the Nordic-affiliated authors in 12 leading journals in the period 2018-2019 and then analysing their total research output throughout their careers in both educational and non-educational publications. Our study analyses a sample of 3237 publications from 76 Nordic authors and provides data on the percentage of their publications that are educationally focused and how this in turn impacts their h-index. We also calculated how early in their career they published their first educational paper.

2 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quantitative scientometric approach to build an understanding of the characteristics of researchers who are affiliated to higher education institutions in Denmark, Finland, Norway or Sweden and are active in the field of EER.

2.1 Data Sources

Data were gathered from the Scopus API (<http://api.elsevier.com> and <http://www.scopus.com>) during January-February 2021 using the pybliometrics Python library [17]. A list of engineering education researchers who were affiliated to institutions in Denmark, Finland, Norway or Sweden was required. To build this list, twelve research journals relevant to the field of engineering education were consulted; these are shown in Table 1. In total, 76 authors were sourced from the four countries.

Following this, details for each author were retrieved from Scopus, including their complete list of publications. For subsequent analysis, only articles, conference papers, reviews, book, and book chapters were included. Other types of publication such as editorials, notes, letters, or erratum were excluded.

Table 1: Engineering education journals where authors were sourced from (note it was possible that authors may have published in multiple journals)

Journal	Acronym	Denmark Authors	Finland Authors	Norway Authors	Sweden Authors
Advances in Engineering Education	AEE	0	0	0	0
Australasian Journal of Engineering Education	AJEE	0	0	0	0
European Journal of Engineering Education	EJEE	7	14	4	20
Global Journal of Engineering Education	GJEE	0	1	0	0
IEEE Transactions on Education	IEEE ToE	2	1	0	1
International Journal of Electrical Engineering Education	IJEEE	0	1	0	0
International Journal of Engineering Education	IJEE	4	2	3	9
International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy	IJEP	0	2	0	0
International Journal of Mechanical Engineering Education	IJMEE	0	0	1	0
Journal of Engineering Education	JEE	0	0	0	0
Journal of Engineering Education Transformations	JEET	3	0	0	0
Journal of Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice (now Journal of Civil Engineering Education)	JPIEEP	0	0	1	0
Total (duplicate authors removed)		16	21	9	30

For each publication, the document title, author keywords, document publication year, source title (e.g., JEE), document type (e.g., article), source type (e.g., journal), publisher, subject category, citation count (note that this can change over time; this is a limitation of the study), and DOI was recorded. A total of 3,237 publications until the end of December 2020 were recorded for the 76 authors.

2.2 Data Analysis

Each publication was categorised as being either educationally focused or non-educationally focused. This allowed information (e.g. citations, h-index) about an author's educational and non-educational publications to be established. Each publication was retrieved from the Scopus API (represented as a Scopus AbstractRetrieval object - see [14]), and the following data fields were searched; document title, source (journal) title, author keywords, subject category, publisher.

After an initial scoping search, the following keyword terms were adopted; 'education', 'student', 'university', 'college', 'ASEE', 'SEFI', 'AAEE'. A publication was deemed to be educational if any of the data fields contained any of the search terms. This method was validated using a random sample of 150 publications.

For each of the 76 authors, several details were then established. This included:

- the number of years the author had been publishing, and how long they had been publishing educational papers
- the percentage of publications which were educationally focussed
- the number of citations on educational and non-educational publications
- the author's overall h-index, h-index of their educational publications, h-index of their non-educational publications
- the distribution of the publications by document type including articles, conference papers, book chapters, books, and reviews.

Tests of statistical significance and correlations were evaluated using SPSSv26.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Publication breakdown

Overall, on a country-wide basis, 449 publications were from Danish authors (362 educational, 87 non-educational), 1281 publications were from Finnish authors (294 educational, 987 non-educational), 405 publications were from Norwegian authors (96 educational, 309 non-educational), and 1102 publications were from Swedish authors (482 educational, 620 non-educational). Figures 1 and 2 show the distribution for the number of publications per author, and the number of citations for each author's publications.

Figure 1: Total number of publications per author author

Figure 2: Total number of citations per author

3.2 Average percentage of publications which are of each document type

Table 2: The mean percentage of authors' publications which are educationally focused for each document type, per country

Country	Type of Document	Article	Book	Chapter (Book)	Conference Paper	Review	Total
Denmark	Educational	31.2%	0.5%	6.3%	38.0%	1.5%	77.5%
	Non-educational	12.1%	0.0%	3.3%	6.4%	0.7%	22.5%
Finland	Educational	33.1%	0.0%	1.4%	30.5%	0.1%	65.0%
	Non-educational	13.4%	0.0%	2.0%	18.6%	0.9%	35.0%
Norway	Educational	22.4%	0.0%	4.5%	9.4%	0.8%	37.1%
	Non-educational	22.3%	0.0%	3.0%	37.1%	0.5%	62.9%
Sweden	Educational	29.6%	0.6%	1.4%	32.8%	0.6%	64.9%
	Non-educational	18.1%	0.0%	0.7%	15.2%	1.1%	35.1%

Authors from Denmark (77.5%), Sweden (64.9%) and Finland (65.0%) published more educational publications than non-educational, while authors from Norway (37.1%) published more non-educational publications than educational publications (Table 2). The mean number of educational and non-educational publications for each country was then compared for statistical significance, using the one-way ANOVA test of significance. This demonstrated there was no statistical significance for the four countries between the mean number of educational publications and

mean number of non-educational publications. This may be due to the small sample sizes of the groups.

Authors from each of the four countries tended to publish a similar amount of journal articles and conference papers, on average. For example, Swedish authors have a publication record which comprises 47.7% articles, and 48% conference papers on average, while Finnish authors have a publication record which comprises 44.7% articles and 46.5% conference papers. There are similar statistics for Denmark (43.4 articles, 44.4 conference papers) and Norway (44.7% articles, 46.5% conference papers). This demonstrates that authors from each of the four countries tend to have a similar distribution of publications when considering document type.

3.3 Average percentage of citations which occur for each document type

Whereas authors from each country tended to publish about 45-49% of their publications as articles and conference papers (Table 2), the publications which received citations were not as evenly distributed (Table 3). Regardless of whether total publications, educational publications, or non-educational publication categories are considered, articles consistently had a higher number of citations compared to conference papers.

Table 3: The mean percentage of authors' citations which occur on each publication type

Country	Type of Document	Article	Book	Chapter (Book)	Conference Paper	Review	Total
Denmark	Educational	59.4%	0.9%	3.6%	14.1%	2.1%	80.1%
	Non-educational	12.8%	0.0%	1.6%	4.7%	0.8%	19.9%
Finland	Educational	39.8%	0.0%	0.5%	28.4%	0.0%	68.7%
	Non-educational	17.3%	0.0%	0.2%	12.6%	1.1%	31.3%
Norway	Educational	20.2%	0.0%	0.1%	3.8%	0.3%	24.4%
	Non-educational	45.1%	0.0%	2.1%	25.3%	3.1%	75.6%
Sweden	Educational	35.6%	5.2%	0.1%	16.3%	1.5%	58.7%
	Non-educational	25.6%	0.0%	0.6%	12.0%	3.0%	41.3%

Table 4: Comparison between mean percentage of publications which are educational, and mean percentage of citations which occur on educational publications

Authors from each country	Mean % of publications which are educational	Mean % of citations on educational publications	Mean % of publications which are non-educational	Mean % of citations on non-educational publications
Denmark (N=16)	77.5	80.1	22.5	19.9
Finland (N=21)	65.0	68.7	35.0	31.3
Norway (N=9)	37.1	24.4	62.9	75.6
Sweden (N=30)	64.9	58.7	35.1	41.3

Table 4 presents a comparison between the mean percentage of publications from

each country which are educational, and the mean percentage of citations which occur on educational publications. As shown, the ratio of educational publications and citations on education publications are similar for Denmark (2.6% difference) and Finland (3.7% difference), but somewhat different for Norway (12.7% difference) and Sweden (6.2% difference).

3.4 h-index

Figure 3 demonstrates that the h-index of authors from Denmark is primarily driven by educational publications, while the h-index of authors from Norway is primarily driven by non-educational publications. Swedish authors benefit slightly more from educational than non-educational publications. Educational and non-educational publications have nearly an identical impact on the h-index of authors from Finland. Considering the 76 combined authors from all four countries, the correlation between overall h-index and educational h-index was statistically significant (Pearson correlation coefficient=0.341, $p < 0.01$), but the correlation between overall h-index and non-educational h-index was notably stronger (Pearson correlation coefficient=0.879, $p < 0.01$).

Figure 3: Mean h-index for each author per country for (i) all publications, (ii) educational publications, and (iii) non-educational publications

3.5 Evolution of Publication Careers

Figure 4: Mean number of years into a researcher's career before an educational publication is published

Figure 4 shows that many EE researchers start their careers publishing educational research. Between the four countries, 41 out of 76 (54%) authors published their first educational publication during their first year of producing research publications. The mean duration of time until producing an educational publication was 4.53 years, but the median was 0 years (because over half of the authors published educational papers at the start of their career). This contrasts with research showing that Australian EE authors tend to publish their first educational publication after 7 years (both mean and median were about 7 years) [15] and in Portugal and Spain it is typically after 6 years [17].

4 SUMMARY

Our findings represent a snapshot of EE researchers in the Nordic countries who published in any of 12 EER journals in the 2018-2019.

Less Norwegian authors appear in our sample than those from the other three countries. This could suggest that EE research is more of a priority in Denmark, Sweden and Finland than in Norway; this interpretation is supported by the data showing that the EE researchers from the former 3 countries published more in the field of EE than other in other fields throughout their career whereas for the Norwegian authors the opposite was the case.

EE authors from all 4 countries had broadly equal publication output for conferences and journals which suggests that presenting and discussing research in conferences is seen as important in the Nordic countries. Journal articles, however, were more likely to gather citations than conference papers.

The h-index of authors from Denmark is primarily driven by educational publications, that of authors from Norway is primarily driven by non-educational publications while for Sweden and Finland the respective impact of the fields of inquiry were more evenly balanced.

Apart from Norway, researchers in our sample began publishing in EE early in their publishing careers. We found this surprising as data from other countries showed that researchers typically began publishing in EE some years after they had published in specialist engineering fields.

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